

Of 80 inoculated plants, 68 showed symptoms. Numbers of plants showing visible symptoms increased with an increase in leafhopper population (see table). Plants containing RTBV + RTSV increased with insect load. There were no clear trends in number of plants containing RTBV or RTSV. All 80 inoculated plants were also serologically tested; serological and transmission identification of RTV virus particles agreed. □

Identifying tungro viruses (RTBV and RTSV) by the transmission method with different levels of leafhoppers. Cuttack, India.

Leafhoppers used for inoculation (no.)	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (no.)				Healthy plants (no.)
		Visual observation	Transmission method			
			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
1	20	13	12	3	2	3
2	20	16	14	3	2	1
3	20	19	16	3	0	1
5	20	20	18	2	0	0

Effect of coal tar-coated urea on brown spot (BS)

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Nitrogen level can be used to manage BS *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan incidence. Its effect varies with level and fertilizer type.

Coal tar-coated and commercial urea at 100 kg N/ha were compared. Urea was mixed with coal tar melted over a low flame and dissolved in kerosene at 1 kg of coal tar and 1.5

Effect of coal tar-coated urea on BS incidence, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Disease intensity ^a			Yield ^b (t/ha)	
	IR20	ADT36	TKM9	IR20	ADT36
Commercial urea	4.8	3.3	4.5	2.6	2.2
Coal tar-coated urea	1.9	2.7	2.2	2.8	2.5
No N	4.3	3.3	3.3	1.3	1.5
CD	0.4	0.5	0.7	0.1	0.2

^a Assessed using the *Standard evaluation system* for rice 0-9 scale. ^b No yield data could be recorded for TKM9 because of heavy rat damage.

liters kerosene/100 kg urea. All the coal tar-coated urea was applied basally at transplanting; commercial urea was applied in three splits.

Coal tar-coated urea uniformly decreased BS incidence and increased yields of IR20 and ADT36 (see table). □

Effect of density on sheath blight (ShB) incidence

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We studied the relation between sowing density (seed rate) and incidence of ShB *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn.

The experiment had 3 replications in a randomized complete block design. Plot size was 6 × 3 m. Rice varieties BW100 (samba-type grains) and BG400-1 (long grains) were broadcast at different seeding rates: recommended by the Department of Agriculture (DR), 0.5 × DR, 1.5 × DR, and 2 × DR).

Seven-day-old *R. solani* culture on rice grains were inoculated by evenly

ShB incidence and yield at different seeding rates. Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Variety	Seeding rate (kg/ha)	Disease incidence ^a (%)		Yield (t/ha)	
		1982-83	1983-84	1982-83	1983-84
BG400-1 (long grain)	100 (DR)	54.1	54.1	3.9	3.0
	50	40.2	40.3	4.4	3.1
	150	57.3	58.0	3.8	3.3
	200	66.3	65.6	4.0	2.7
BW100 (samba-type grain)	15 (DR)	55.1	57.1	4.1	3.0
	31.5	44.8	42.8	3.6	3.1
	112.5	61.9	67.9	3.4	2.7
	150	11.1	69.4	3.5	2.6

^a LSD (P = 0.05) = 12.5 for 1982-83 and 5.1 for 1983-84. The correlation between disease incidence and seeding rate was positive and linear in both seasons: $r = 0.913^{**}$ for BW100 and 0.719^{**} for BG400-1 in 1982-83, and 0.88^{**} for BW100 and 0.75^{**} for BG400-1 in 1983-84.

spreading the grains on the water surface at panicle initiation. Recommended fertilization was applied and standard plant protection measures were taken.

Disease incidence was assessed at harvest. The number of tillers with

infected flag leaf and total number of tillers within a 1-m² quadrat from each plot were recorded and the disease incidence percentage was computed:

$$\% \text{ of flag leaf infection} = \frac{\text{no. of tillers with infected flag leaf/m}^2}{\text{total no. of tillers/m}^2} \times 100$$

Grains were air-dried and weighed, and yield calculated, leaving a 30-cm border around each plot.

Disease incidence and yield at different seed rates are given in the table. The expected yield increase with higher

plant densities was not found. Higher disease incidence affected yield. □

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Persistent toxicity of three modified formulations of carbofuran to brown planthopper (BPH) in India

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The Regional Research Laboratory (Hyderabad, India) supplied polyethylene-based and lignin-based formulations of carbofuran reported to be slow releasing in nature. We studied their persistent toxicity to BPH compared to that of commercially available encapsulated granules of carbofuran in a confined cage experiment Jun-Jul 1985.

The treatments were in a factorial combination of 3 formulations of carbofuran (polyethylene-based, lignin-based, and encapsulated) and 2 application rates (0.75 and 1.50 kg ai/ha).

The formulations were broadcast into the floodwater at 0.75 and 1.5 kg ai/ha 5 d after transplanting (DT). Starting 3 d after treatment, toxicity was monitored weekly using the BPH bioassay technique.

Toxicity of polyethylene-based and

Mortality of BPH adults, at various days after treatment, on rice plants in fields that received modified formulations of carbofuran at 2 rates. Trivandrum, India, 1985.

encapsulated preparations persisted at a higher level and longer than did toxicity of the lignin-based granule (see figure). Mortality remained consistently higher with 1.5 kg ai/ha to 50 DT.

The persistent toxicity differed with rate of application, with a significant interaction between formulation and rate of application.

Mortality decline (4.7% /d) was lowest with the polyethylene-based formulation at 1.5 kg ai/ha, closely followed by polyethylene-based formulation at 0.75 kg ai/ha and encapsulated formulation at 1.5 kg ai/ha. Mortality declined at a faster rate in the lignin-based formulation. Release of the active ingredient appeared to differ with formulation. □

Epidemiology of rice tungro virus (RTV) in 1984-85 kharif, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu

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During 1984-85 kharif (May-Aug) the rice crop in Chingleput District was completely devastated by an unprecedented outbreak of RTV. Crops planted early the next season

(samba, Sep-Jan) were also severely affected.

We studied the epidemiology of the disease in a field experiment, laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Nine plantings of 25-d-old CO 43 seedlings were staggered at 10-d intervals starting 10 Aug 1984. Seedlings were transplanted in 3- × 3-m plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Recommended agronomic practices were followed and 100-50-50

kg NPK/ha applied. All the P₂O₅ and K₂O were applied basally along with 50% N. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 15 and 30 d after transplanting (DT).

RTV incidence was assessed at 45 DT. The number of green leafhoppers collected in light traps Aug-Nov was recorded by month.

RTV incidence in the field correlated positively with the field population of the vector *Nephotettix*